

Synthesis and characterization of Pb^{II}, Sn^{II}, Hg^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with Schiff base of aminothiazoles

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Some new complexes of Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} of the type [M(X)₂(L)] (where X = Cl, Br and L = Schiff base ligand of aminothiazoles) have been synthesised and characterized by physicochemical methods.

Schiff bases obtained from *o*-hydroxyaldehydes have strong ability to form metal complexes¹. Thiazole exhibit a wide range of biological activities and therefore Schiff bases of aminothiazoles are expected to be biologically active². More *et al.* have studied the preparation and the physicochemical studies on the metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from 4-aryl-2-aminothiazoles and substituted salicylaldehyde and have studied bioactivity of a series of new Schiff bases derived from 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole and substituted salicylaldehydes³. This paper deals with the reaction of MCl₂ (M = Sn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Hg^{II}, Zn^{II}) and Schiff bases of aminothiazole.

Results and discussion

These newly synthesized complexes were coloured and

stable at room temperature. The elemental analysis and molar conductance data were listed in Table 1. The low molar conductance of these complexes indicates that they are non-electrolyte.

All the complexes have shown $\nu_{C=N}$ band at 1620–1610 cm⁻¹ and ν_{OH} (phenolic) at 2880–2860 cm⁻¹, which normally appears at 1630 cm⁻¹ (for $\nu_{C=N}$) and at 2900 cm⁻¹ (for ν_{OH}) in the free ligand³. The shifting of these bands to lower wave numbers in the complexes indicates the coordination of nitrogen atoms of azomethine group and phenolic OH group⁴.

The photoelectron peak binding energy data of all these metal ions are : M2p_{3/2}, for Hg^{II} 676.4, Zn^{II} 86.4, Sn^{II} 713.8

Table 1. Analytical data of MX₂.L complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Found (Calcd.) %			Molar conductance in acetone (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
		C	H	N	
1.	[Hg(Cl) ₂ (L ¹)]	35.8 (36.0)	2.2 (2.4)	4.8 (4.9)	30
2.	[Hg(Cl) ₂ (L ²)]	30.2 (30.4)	1.6 (1.7)	4.2 (4.4)	26
3.	[Hg(Cl) ₂ (L ³)]	31.4 (31.7)	1.6 (1.7)	4.1 (4.3)	28
4.	[Hg(Cl) ₂ (L ⁴)]	27.2 (27.4)	1.0 (1.2)	4.0 (4.0)	25
5.	[Zn(Cl) ₂ (L ¹)]	47.1 (47.3)	3.0 (3.2)	6.4 (6.5)	22
6.	[Zn(Cl) ₂ (L ²)]	38.4 (38.7)	2.0 (2.2)	5.2 (5.6)	28
7.	[Zn(Cl) ₂ (L ³)]	40.0 (40.2)	2.0 (2.1)	5.4 (5.5)	25
8.	[Zn(Cl) ₂ (L ⁴)]	34.2 (34.4)	1.4 (1.5)	4.8 (4.9)	26
9.	[Sn(Cl) ₂ (L ¹)]	42.0 (42.1)	2.4 (2.8)	5.6 (5.7)	30
10.	[Sn(Cl) ₂ (L ²)]	34.6 (34.9)	2.0 (2.0)	5.0 (5.1)	26
11.	[Sn(Cl) ₂ (L ³)]	36.2 (36.3)	1.8 (1.9)	4.8 (4.9)	27
12.	[Sn(Cl) ₂ (L ⁴)]	31.2 (31.0)	1.2 (1.4)	4.4 (4.5)	22
13.	[Pb(Cl) ₂ (L ¹)]	35.4 (35.6)	2.2 (2.4)	4.6 (4.8)	25
14.	[Pb(Cl) ₂ (L ²)]	30.0 (30.1)	1.6 (1.7)	4.2 (4.3)	24
15.	[Pb(Cl) ₂ (L ³)]	32.2 (32.0)	1.6 (1.6)	4.1 (4.3)	24
16.	[Pb(Cl) ₂ (L ⁴)]	27.0 (27.1)	1.0 (1.2)	3.8 (3.9)	20

and Pb^{II} 763.6 and their complexes are N1S 400.2–403.6; O1s 532.6 and S2p 165.4. This suggested more effective positive charge on nitrogen atom in metal complexes than free ligand due to coordination of nitrogen with metal ions in these complexes⁵. This was observed during the analysis of O1s and S2p that O1s photoelectron peak binding energy was increased in all metal complexes than free ligand but S2p binding energy remains same as in free ligand and metal complexes. This concludes oxygen atom is involved in the coordination in these metal complexes, while there is no involvement of sulphur atom in metal complexes for coordination.

On the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity, IR and X-ray photoelectron data identifying the site of coordination, it is possible to assign the structure of each complex.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were double-distilled before use.

Preparation of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole⁶ :

4-Phenyl-2-aminothiazole was prepared by the reaction of acetophenone (1 mmol, 12 g) with thiourea (2 mmol, 15.2 g) and iodine (1 mmol, 25.4 g). The base was purified by recrystallisation from alcohol.

Preparation of 4-(p-bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole⁶ :

4-(p-Bromophenyl)-2-aminothiazole was prepared by the reaction of p-bromoacetophenone (1 mmol, 19.9 g) with thiourea (2 mmol, 15.2 g) and iodine (1 mmol, 25.4 g). The base was purified by recrystallisation from alcohol.

Preparation of Schiff bases⁷ :

The following four Schiff bases were prepared by con-

densation of equimolar amounts of *o*-hydroxyaldehyde or substituted *o*-hydroxyaldehyde and substituted 2-aminothiazole in ethanol. The crystals were obtained on cooling the solution in ethanol and dried over reduced pressure³. m.p. (°C) $L^1 = 152^\circ$; $L^2 = 172^\circ$; $L^3 = 187^\circ$; $L^4 = 181^\circ$.

Synthesis of metal complex :

The metal salts (MCl_2) (1 mmol, 0.472 g for $HgCl_2$ or 0.1896 g for $SnCl_2$ or 0.278 g for $PbCl_2$ or 0.136 g for $ZnCl_2$) in ethanol (20 ml) was mixed with solution of Schiff base ligand (1 mmol, 0.298 g for L^1 , 0.347 g for L^2 , 0.361 g for L^3 and 0.381 g for L^4 Schiff base) in ethanol (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h and solid product was filtered, washed with dry ethanol and air dried.

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References

1. R. H. Holm, G. W. Everett and A. Chakravorty, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **7**, 83.
2. I. Saikama and S. Takano, *Chem. Abst.*, 1971, **74**, 3604; D. E. Dickson, *Chem. Abst.*, 1962, **56**, 475; D. Lednicer, *Chem. Abst.*, 1970, **72**, 17772.
3. C. K. Bhaskare and P. G. More, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1966, **25**, 166; P. G. More and T. N. Powar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 154; P. G. More, R. B. Bhalvankar and S. C. Pattar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 474.
4. T. N. Srivastava, A. K. S. Chauhan and G. K. Mehrotra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, **22**, 712; Minoro Tanka, H. Kurosawa and R. Okawara, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1967, **3**, 565.
5. Shekhar Srivastava, *Applied Spectrosc. Rev.*, 1986, **22**, 401.
6. B. Dash and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 663.